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(Talabalarning III an‘naviy ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari)

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IX SHO‘BA. TALABALARNING INNOVATSION G‘OYALARI

AN EFFECTIVE MODEL OF ESTABLISHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES (ESP) COURSES FOR TRANSLATORS

Esanov Azizbek ‡

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola O‘zbekistondagi chet tillarni o‘rganish va o‘qitish tizimining hozirgi holati va maqsadli yo‘naltirilgan ingliz tili (ESP) kurslarining ingliz tili to‘g‘risida turli sohalardagi insonlar, xususan tarjimonlarning xabardorligini oshirishga qaratilgan. O‘zbekistondagi tarjimonlar uchun samarali ESP kurslarini joriy etish bo‘yicha yetakchi olimlar va tadqiqotchilarning fikrlari hisobga olingan. Muallif ushbu maqolasida ona tili ingliz tili bo‘lmagan tarjimonlarga tarjima masalalarini o‘rgatish kursining modelini taklif etgan.

Tayanch so‘zlar: xorijiy tillarni o‘rganish va o‘qitish, maqsadli yo‘naltirilgan ingliz tili, tarjima va tarjimashunoslik.

Annotation

This article discusses current state of foreign language learning and teaching system in Uzbekistan and the importance of ESP courses for the improvement of the awareness of the people from different fields of study about the English language, especially of translators. Leading scientists and researchers’ points of view about ESP courses are taken into account to make a clear observe to implement an effective ESP courses for translators in Uzbekistan. Author proposes a model of the course of teaching translation issues and subject to translators whose language is not English.

Key words: Foreign language learning and teaching, English for Specific Pusposes, translation.

The modern situation in Uzbekistan can be characterized by innovative processes in all spheres including education. Foreign languages play an important role in the country’s educational politics and according to State Education Standards this discipline is obligatory to study at every secondary school and higher educational institution not depending on professional direction. According to the Decree of the First President of the Republic of

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Uzbekistan Islam Karimov "On measures for further improvement of foreign languages learning" (December 10, 2012), there has been a considerable development in the sphere of foreign languages learning and this process is now in progress at all stages of teaching foreign languages (FLT). The modern model of teaching and learning English in Uzbekistan can be described as the following: "In Uzbekistan ELT is seen as a career in a field of educational specialization: it requires a specialized knowledge base obtained through both academic study and practical experience" [1, 9]. In order to do this, various textbooks and manuals, modern innovative methods and techniques and other kind of means are being put into practice. However, there is still the need for implementing the modern standard of systematic, continuous mechanism for effective FLT system considering recent achievements, especially for English for Specific Purposes: translation (ESP) in Uzbekistan. As this branch of linguistics is rather new direction in FLT in Uzbekistan. In this case, it is important to define the term ESP and its peculiar aspects so as to work out efficient outcome for foreign language learners, as well as translators.

According to Basri Salim, English for Specific Purposes courses are designed for learners planning to study in a specific field that is delivered in English, such as business, law, computers and others and for learners who study in specific field in different language and they need or want to know specific vocabulary, terms, and other relevant things in English from their field. [2,747] On the contrary, Robinson claims that "what is considered "specific" about ESP in a given location in the world may not be considered the same elsewhere. Thus, it is impossible to provide a certain definition for ESP which could be constant anywhere" [3, 1]. To our point of view, the main component of ESP is to teach people from all fields of study effectively considering their background knowledge and recent development in their specific directions. And this requires teachers of ESP to have at least a good proficiency not only in English language, but also in the chosen branches they teach.

Currently, modern trends of teaching ESP, along with ESP for translators is of great importance, as this assists specialists in different fields to have general knowledge about English language and to acquire skills to comprehend needed materials in the language. The most sophisticated issue about ESP for translators is to provide skillful teachers and sufficient textbooks with relevant information and context and to make ESP courses available with effective syllabus that focuses on the content of translation process and takes background knowledge of students in consideration.

To our viewpoint, the following sample subject syllabus can be an effective tool for the productive establishment of ESP for translation courses:

Introduction
• What is translation?
• Why is translation useful?
• Translation theories and studies
• Overview of the English and Uzbek language systems
Comparing and Contrasting Uzbek and English Grammatical Structures
• Word category
• Passive construction
• Negation
• Existential construction
• Ellipsis
• Inversion
Comparing and Contrasting the Uzbek and English Lexicon
• Frequency of verbs and nouns
• Words similar in meaning
• Markedly different expressions
• Collocations
• Appropriateness
• Idiomatic expressions
Common errors in translation
• Semantic errors
• Syntactic errors
• Lexical errors

• Errors related to culture
• Errors as a result of direction translation
Translation skills
• Types of translation skills (e.g. transliteration, free translation, etc.)
• Translation techniques (e.g. deduction, alternation, conversion, etc.)
Translation and culture
• Historical backgrounds
• Customs
• Political systems, religious beliefs, world views and translation
• Cultural conflicts

The ESP courses for translators with such subject synopsis have aims to explore the practical issues that arise in language-to-language translation, especially in the context of Uzbek into English so as to raise students' awareness of the differences and similarities between to the two language systems.

In conclusion, ESP courses for translators having careful analysis and future aims with sufficient plan will always bring an expected results, as long as they consider students' prior knowledge and the level of materials. This can be an solution to the case in compilation of ESP for translators whose language is not English.

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